

Synthesis, characterization and coordinating properties of an NNS donor system, 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole-3-pyrrolidinylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzPyr), and its cobalt(III), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes

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Abstract : The ligational behaviour of 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole-3-pyrrolidinylthiosemicarbazone has been demonstrated by isolation and characterisation of its complexes with cobalt(III), nickel(II) and copper(II) with different counterions. Magnetic and spectral features indicate $[\text{Co}(\text{MPzPyr})_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_3, \text{ClO}_4$ or BF_4) as the diamagnetic octahedral species with the ligand in the deprotonated thiol form, while $[\text{Ni}(\text{HMPzPyr})_2]\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or NO_3) is proposed as octahedral complex with the ligand in the neutral thione form. However, at pH ~6, nickel(II) salts afford octahedral bis-nickel(II) complex, $\text{Ni}(\text{MPzPyr})_2$, while copper(II) salts in acetonitrile medium give $\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or NO_3) with the deprotonated ligand. IR spectra indicate that the pyrazolyl ring nitrogen (²N), the azomethine nitrogen and the sulphur atom are the points of attachment with the metal ion in all these complex species. The cyclic voltammetric study of copper(II) complexes reveals the quasi-reversible one-electron process ($\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$), where the EPR data confirm the presence of $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state of these complexes.

Keywords : Synthesis, spectroscopy, cobalt(III), nickel(II), copper(II) complexes, pyrazolylthiosemicarbazone.

Introduction

The well-documented biological activities of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones as well as their metal complexes have attracted much attention over the years^{1,2}. The five member heterocycle pyrazole (1 : 2 diazole) is isomeric with imidazole (1 : 3 diazole), an integral part of histidine, and both have rich coordination chemistry. A number of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones, are well known for their antitumor³, antiviral⁴, antibacterials, antimalarial⁶ and antifungal⁷ activities, and such activities have often been related to their chelating abilities towards

one or more essential trace metal ions. Being fascinated by significant biological implications of transition metal complexes of various thiosemicarbazones, a comprehensive program has been taken up to study the synthesis, characterization and coordination properties of new pyrazole-based thiosemicarbazones, which might have potential biological importance. The present communication intends to report the synthesis, characterization and coordination mode of a new pyrazole-derived thiosemicarbazone viz. 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole-3-pyrrolidinylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzPyr) having the following thione-thione forms.

Results and discussion

Ligand characterization :

The ligand, HMPzPyr, has been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis (C, H and N), IR, PMR and mass spectra (Table 1). The characteristic IR bands (Table 2) at 3200–3100, 1620 ($\nu_{C=N(pz)}$), 1570 ($\nu_{CH=N}$), 1010 (ν_{N-NPz}) and 860 ($\nu_{C=S}$) cm^{-1} are in good agreement with composition $C_{10}H_{15}N_5S$ and structural formulation as figured earlier. The ligand molecule has a proton adjacent to the thiocarbonyl group and consequently can exhibit thione-thiol tautomerism. The IR spectrum does not display any (ν_{S-H}) band near 2600 cm^{-1} , but exhibit (ν_{NH}) bands in the range 3100–3200 cm^{-1} , indicating that the ligand remains in the thioketo tautomer in the solid state. A signal at low field (δ 13.36) in the 1H NMR spectrum corresponds to the NH proton of the pyrazole ring (Table 4). The thione-thiol tautomerism of the ligand in solution is also indicated by another low field signal (δ 12.65) due to formation of S---H bond^{8,9}. Two singlets appear at δ 2.26 (3H) and δ 6.31 (1H) assigned to 5-CH₃ and 4CH protons in pyrazole ring respectively. Another singlet (δ 7.30) corresponds to azomethine (-CH=N-) proton. Signals in the range δ 1.18–1.31 are due to the pyrrolidiny protons. The mass fragmentation patterns are also compatible with the proposed structural formulation with the strongest molecular ion peak appears at m/z 237 along with a subsequent strong peak at m/z 166 for a loss of the pyrrolidine unit. The immediate next molecular ion peak at m/z 107 is due to loss of pyrrolidine-thioamide (130 unit) followed by a secondary fragmentation of benzylic type cleavage to expel H from the -CH₃ group to give next peak at m/z 106. The fragment at m/z 91 for thiosemicarbazide, H₂NNHC(S)NH₂, can be accounted for by loss of butadiene unit from pyrrolidiny thiosemicarbazide followed by acquiring -NH₂ group. The molecular ion peaks at m/z 166 and m/z 107 can be reconciled by loss of pyrrolidine (C₄H₉N) and H₂N-C(S)-NC₄H₈ (C₅H₉N₂S) respectively. The schematic diagram showing the possible fragmentations is given below.

Characterization of the complexes :

Analytical and UV-Vis spectral data point out that the reactions of HMPzPyr with cobalt(II) salts in presence of air furnish well-defined diamagnetic complexes of the general composition [Co^{III}(MPzPyr)₂]X (where X = Cl, Br, NO₃, ClO₄ and BF₄) at room temperature (25 °C) (Table 1). Conductivity measurements in DMF solution (carried out within 10 min of the preparation of solution) indicate 1 : 1 electrolytic nature of the complexes in the said solvent¹⁰ ($\Lambda_M = 80-104 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) at room temperature (25 °C). The diffuse reflectance spectra of all the cobalt(III) complexes exhibit four bands in the region 8410–9100, 15220–16200, 17301–19200 and 24155–25255 cm^{-1} . While the first three transitions may be assigned as $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}$ transitions respectively in an idealized O_h symmetry^{11,12}, the fourth transition is probably charge transfer in nature. In view of high molar extinction coefficient values, the electronic spectra of these complexes in DMF (Table 1) show three bands in the regions 36360–38500, 31545–33250 and 24560–25000 cm^{-1} can be ascribed as intra ligand and CT transitions¹³. All the reported nickel(II) complexes conforming to the composition [Ni(HMPzPyr)₂]X₂ (X = Cl, Br and NO₃) and [Ni(MPzPyr)₂] have effective magnetic moment values (Table 1) falling in the range 2.81–3.10 BM (at 303 K). The magnetic data are consistent with the expected values of six-coordinate octahedral nickel(II) species¹³. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the nickel(II) complexes (Table 1) are characterized by three main bands in the region 25200–28245, 17980–20220 and 10070–12200 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned as $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_3), $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) transition in the O_h symmetry, respectively. Similar type of spectral bands are also observed in case of the octahedral nickel(II) complexes with 2-acetylpyridine ⁴N-cyclohexylthiosemicarbazone¹⁴ and ⁴N-substituted thiosemicarbazones of 2-hydroxylacetophenone¹⁵. The electronic spectra in solution are characterized by two

Table 1. Elemental analysis, conductance, magnetic moment and spectral data for the complexes of HMPzPyr

Complex (Color)	Contents (%): Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff}	Δ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	State	Spectral data		$d \rightarrow d$
	C	H	N	M				Wave numbers (log ϵ)	Intraigand and charge transfer	
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]Cl (Reddish brown)	42.3 (42.4)	4.9 (4.9)	25.1 (24.7)	10.3 (10.4)	Diamagnetic	93.5	Solid	-	-	24155, 17300, 15700, 8410
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]Br (Dark brown)	39.0 (39.3)	4.4 (4.6)	23.5 (22.9)	9.6 (9.6)	Diamagnetic	82.2	Solid	-	-	25255, 18200, 15220, 9100
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]NO ₃ (Brown)	40.1 (40.4)	4.6 (4.7)	26.0 (25.9)	9.7 (9.9)	Diamagnetic	85.1	Solution Solid	24625 (4.11), 36360 (4.66), 3145 (4.59)	-	24760, 17500, 16100, 8620
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]ClO ₄ (Reddish brown)	37.9 (38.0)	4.4 (4.4)	23.3 (22.0)	9.3 (9.3)	Diamagnetic	81.3	Solution Solid	25000 (4.11), 38200 (4.74), 33100 (4.58)	-	25050, 19200, 16200, 8815
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]BF ₄ (Deep brown)	38.4 (38.9)	4.4 (4.5)	23.1 (22.7)	9.5 (9.5)	Diamagnetic	81.2	Solution Solid	24970 (4.15), 38500 (4.87), 33250 (4.68)	-	24970, 18860, 15720, 8720
[Ni(HMPzPyr) ₂]Cl ₂ (Deep green)	40.1 (39.8)	4.6 (4.9)	22.8 (23.2)	9.7 (9.7)	2.97	195.5	Solid	-	-	28100, 17980, 11875 18220 (1.53), 12250 (1.81)
[Ni(HMPzPyr) ₂]Br ₂ (Parrot green)	33.6 (34.6)	4.6 (4.3)	19.0 (20.2)	8.4 (8.5)	2.81	180.0	Solid	33200 (4.33), 27845 (4.16)	-	27435, 18130, 12200 17515 (11.53), 11975 (1.86)
[Ni(HMPzPyr) ₂].2NO ₃ (Deep green)	36.3 (36.5)	4.5 (4.6)	26.1 (25.6)	8.8 (8.9)	3.10	181.3	Solid	33445 (4.38), 27250 (4.37)	-	28245, 18100, 11775 17955 (1.56), 11760 (1.72)
[Ni(MPzPyr) ₂] (Reddish green)	44.9 (45.2)	5.1 (5.3)	27.3 (26.4)	11.00 (11.1)	2.92	27.5	Solid	-	-	2500, 20220, 10070 20100 (1.44), 9870 (1.57)
[Cu(MPzPyr)Cl] (Parrot green)	36.0 (35.8)	4.1 (4.2)	20.6 (20.9)	18.8 (18.9)	2.07	13.3	Solution Solid	30300 (4.21), 25375 (4.11)	25445	14285, 14125 15300 (2.11)
[Cu(MPzPyr)Br] (Deep green)	30.7 (31.6)	3.4 (3.7)	18.2 (18.4)	16.4 (16.7)	1.71	7.1	Solid	29240 (4.01)	23865	14950
[Cu(MPzPyr)NO ₃] (Green)	32.8 (33.1)	3.6 (3.9)	24.1 (23.2)	16.9 (17.6)	1.75	17.1	Solid	32260 (3.98)	25500	16665 (2.20) 15230, 14980
[Cu(MPzPyr)ClO ₄] (Green)	29.1 (30.1)	3.3 (3.5)	18.7 (17.5)	15.7 (15.9)	1.79	7.2	Solution Solid	31700 (3.90)	26700	15905 (2.16) 15820, 14970 15900 (2.22)

main bands at 11760–12250 (ν_1) and 17510–20100 cm^{-1} (ν_2), which are not significantly different from those in the solid state. In the solution spectra, the ν_3 band [${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$] expected for an octahedral nickel(II) complex could not be observed, probably due to the occurrence of intense charge transfer bands into the visible position of the spectrum masking the expected $d-d$ bands¹⁶. The copper(II) complexes of HMPzPyr are nonelectrolytes with general composition [Cu(MPzPyr)X] (X = Cl, Br, NO_3 and ClO_4) as ascertained from analytical data. The effective magnetic moment values at room temperature (25 °C) is found to be in the range 1.7–2.1 BM for magnetically dilute copper(II) complexes with d^9 system. The solid state electronic spectra of complexes are dominated by intense intra-ligand bands and charge-transfer bands. However, the spectra have two low intensity bands in the region 14125–16000 cm^{-1} assignable to the $d-d$ bands of planar copper(II) complexes¹⁷. Similar type of spectral bands were also observed for copper(II) complexes of ${}^4\text{N}$, ${}^4\text{N}'$ -disubstituted thiosemicarbazone of 2-acetylpyridine¹⁸.

Infrared spectral studies (4000–200 cm^{-1}) for the free ligand and its complexes (Table 2) reveal that the ligand, HMPzPyr, behaves, in general, as a mono deprotonated NNS tridentate ligand when complexed with Co^{III} and Cu^{II} , while with Ni^{II} , the neutral (NNS) tridentate ligand provides electrolytic Ni^{II} bis-chelate species. The strong IR band appearing at 1570 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{CH}=\text{N}(\text{azom})}$) in the free ligand spectrum has been found to shift to the lower fre-

quency region ($\sim 1560 \text{cm}^{-1}$) in the spectra of the metal complexes due to probable involvement of the azomethine nitrogen in bonding¹⁹. The positive shift of the $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{N}(\text{pz})}$ frequencies from 1010 cm^{-1} (in the free ligand spectrum) to $\sim 1030 \text{cm}^{-1}$ on complexation with a metal ion indicates involvement of the pyrazolyl tertiary nitrogen (${}^2\text{N}$) atom in bonding. An intense band at 860 cm^{-1} in the free ligand spectrum due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ undergoes a downward shift by 30–60 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the metal complexes pointing to the participation of the sulphur atom of the C=S group as a possible coordination site. The above proposition is further supported by the presence of a strong band at $\sim 280 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (absent in the free ligand spectrum) assignable to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}(\text{pz})}$ and bands in the regions ~ 470 and $\sim 380 \text{cm}^{-1}$ attributable to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}(\text{azom})}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{S}}$, respectively.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of diamagnetic cobalt(III) complexes (Table 3) when compared with that of the free ligand show slightly downfield shift of the positions of pyrazolyl ring protons, azomethine proton and pyrrolidinyl ring proton (with different chemical environment) ascribing to the fact that the coordination of the ligand to cobalt(III) centre through pyrazolyl nitrogen (${}^2\text{N}$), azomethine nitrogen and thiolato sulphur reducing electron density at these atoms to different extent. ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra thus provide support for the bonding characteristic of the primary ligand (HMPzPyr) in forming complexes with cobalt(III) through pyrazolyl ring nitrogen (${}^2\text{N}$), azomethine nitrogen and the thiolato sulphur atom².

Table 2. Some characteristic IR bands (in cm^{-1}) of HMPzPyr and its metal complexes

	$\nu_{\text{CH}=\text{N}(\text{azom})}$	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}(\text{pz})}$	$\nu_{\text{N}-\text{N}(\text{pz})}$	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}(\text{pz})}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}(\text{azom})}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{S}}$
HMPzPyr	1570	1440	1010	860	-	-	-
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]Cl	1560	1475	1030	790	275	470	380
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]Br	1555	1500	1030	780	280	475	375
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]NO ₃	1560	1480	1020	830	280	480	360
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]ClO ₄	1560	1470	1040	800	275	475	380
[Co(MPzPyr) ₂]BF ₄	1555	1475	1030	800	270	470	380
[Ni(HMPzPyr) ₂]Cl ₂	1560	1380	1030	820	265	485	365
[Ni(HMPzPyr) ₂]Br ₂	1565	1370	1030	835	270	480	365
[Ni(HMPzPyr) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	1560	1380	1030	830	275	475	370
[Ni(MPzPyr) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1565	1385	1020	840	270	485	365
[Ni(MPzPyr) ₂]	1560	1410	1030	840	280	480	370
[Cu(MPzPyr)Cl]	1490	1380	1080	800	540	330	400
[Cu(MPzPyr)Br]	1450	1350	1050	815	470	290	380
[Cu(MPzPyr)NO ₃]	1480	1375	1080	810	475	300	380
[Cu(MPzPyr)ClO ₄]	1490	1380	1080	815	480	290	390

Table 3. ^1H NMR assignments of HMPzPyr and its cobalt(III) complexes (in δ ppm) relative to TMS

Compd.	Hydrazinic proton	Position of pyrazolyl ring proton			Azomethine proton	Pyrrolidinyl proton
		1	4	5 (CH_3)		
HMPzPyr	12.65	13.36	6.31	2.26	7.30	1.18–1.31
$[\text{Co}(\text{MPzPyr})_2]\text{Cl}$	–	13.80	6.48	2.44	8.32	1.34–2.18
$[\text{Co}(\text{MPzPyr})_2]\text{Br}$	–	13.76	6.47	2.44	8.34	1.33–2.18
$[\text{Co}(\text{MPzPyr})_2]\text{NO}_3$	–	13.75	6.45	2.46	8.34	1.34–2.18
$[\text{Co}(\text{MPzPyr})_2]\text{ClO}_4$	–	13.78	6.46	2.47	8.34	1.36–2.18
$[\text{Co}(\text{MPzPyr})_2]\text{BF}_4$	–	13.76	6.46	2.47	8.33	1.36–2.18

The electronic spin-resonance spectra of the copper(II) complexes (Table 4) in the polycrystalline state at room temperature (25 °C) show a strong signal at high field

Table 4. EPR spectral parameters of copper(II) complexes of HMPzPyr

Compd.	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{Cl}]$	2.12	2.03	2.06
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{Br}]$	2.14	2.06	2.09
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{NO}_3]$	2.16	2.08	2.10
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{ClO}_4]$	2.12	2.06	2.08

and a weaker one at low field corresponding to g_{\perp} and g_{\parallel} respectively. The representative EPR spectra of complexes are given in Fig. 1. However, g_{\parallel} values of all the com-

plexes in the series indicate that the bonding is dominated by the ligand moiety rather than the counter ions. The g_{\parallel} values being less than 2.3 are also indicative of significant covalent bonding in the complexes and suggestive of coordination of the ligand to metal through nitrogen and sulphur in agreement with IR results. Further for all the complexes observed g values, $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.00$ and the G values in the range 3–5 are consistent with a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state having a small exchange coupling^{20,21}. It can be reconciled, therefore, that the absorption band in the electronic spectrum at $14970\text{--}14125\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$ and the other at $15825\text{--}14300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xz/yz}$.

The electrochemical properties of copper(II) complexes were studied with cyclic voltammetry. The results of

Fig. 1. Solid state X-band EPR spectra of the copper(II) complexes : $[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{Cl}]$ (a) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{Br}]$ (b).

voltammetric studies of the representative $[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{X}]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ and Br) complexes are given in Table 5 and corresponding cyclic voltammograms are shown in Fig. 2. A, C, E, F etc. indicate the identified reduction-oxidation peaks. The peak A and B represent the reduc-

and used without further purification. Spectrograde solvent were used for spectral and conductance measurements. DMSO- d_6 (Sigma) was used as solvent for recording NMR spectra. Solvents were distilled before use in the synthesis. The mass spectrum of the ligand was re-

Table 5. Cyclic voltammetric data for the copper(II) complexes of HMPzPyr in DMSO solution containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl-ammonium perchlorate on a Pt-electrode at a scan rate of 100 mV/s

Compd.	E_p (A)	E_p (C)	$E^{0}_{1/2}$	$i_{p,a}/i_{p,c}$	E_p (E)	E_p (F)	E_p (G)	E_p (H)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{Cl}]$	-0.600	-0.360	-0.480	0.82	+0.310	+0.400	-0.04	+0.260
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{Br}]$	-0.504	-0.240	-0.372	0.86	+0.214	+0.378	-	-

Fig 2. Cyclic voltammogram of the copper(II) complexes : $[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{Cl}]$ (a) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{Br}]$ (b).

tion of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ and subsequent oxidation of $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$, respectively. The separation between peak A and C within the scan rates employed are characteristic of an apparent quasi-reversible one-electron process. For chlorocomplex, there is a quasi-reversible reduction at -0.48 V which is tentatively assigned to $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ couple. The relatively large ΔE_p ($E_{p,a} - E_{p,c}$) value probably reflects the relaxation process involved in a stereochemical change from planar copper(II) to tetrahedral copper(I)²². It has been shown that the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ redox processes are influenced by coordination number, stereochemistry and the hard/soft character of the donor atom(s)^{23,24}. The peak G probably corresponds to the reduction of the solvolyzed mono-cationic species $[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})(\text{DMSO})]^+$, deprotonated thiosemicarbazone ligand, as thiolato ligands are known to be easily oxidizable.

Experimental

Reagents and techniques :

All the chemicals used were of GR/AR grade quality

recorded in a Jeol D-300 (EI/CI). The PMR spectrum of the ligand and of the diamagnetic cobalt(III) complexes were recorded in d_6 -DMSO with Bruker AM 300L (300 MHz) super conducting FT-NMR. The electronic spectra in the solution of the complexes were recorded in Hitachi UV 2100 spectrophotometer, while the solid-state diffuse reflectance spectra employed a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer. Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities of the solid metal complexes were measured in PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer. The IR spectra of the ligand and of the metal complexes were recorded in Perkin-Elmer model 833 infrared spectrophotometer (4000-200 cm^{-1}) using KBr pellets. The molar conductances of the complexes were recorded by using Systronics 303 model Conductivity Bridge using a solution of 10^{-3} M concentration. The electron paramagnetic resonance spectra (EPR) of the copper(II) complexes were recorded on a Varian model E-112 spectrometer (X-band) in the polycrystalline state at room temperature using DPPH ($g = 2.0036$)

as a calibrant. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded with a cyclic voltammetry model 270/250 Research Electrochemistry software (version 4.23) in DMSO solution of the species (10^{-3} M) using tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (NBu_4ClO_4 ; 0.1 M) as supporting electrolyte, Pt-electrode as working electrode and standard calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode using scan rate 100 mV/s.

Synthesis of the ligand :

The reaction detail of the ligand was given below for ready reference.

Briefly, the ligand HMPzPyr preparation involved (i) the conversion of 5-methylpyrazole-3-carbohydrazide (I) into its benzene sulphonyl derivative (II) (m.p.179–180 °C) followed by (ii) reflux of *S*-methyl- β -*N*-(5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole-3-yl) methylene dithiocarbamate (HMPzSMe) with pyrrolidine base^{25,26}. The recrystallized product melted at 210 °C (yield ~70%) (Found : C, 50.07; H, 6.57; N, 28.75. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{S}$: C, 50.63; H, 6.33; N, 29.53%).

Syntheses of the complexes :

Syntheses of $[\text{Co}(\text{MPzPyr})_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_3, \text{ClO}_4$ and BF_4) : A solution of the ligand, HMPzPyr (0.01 mol, 2.37 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was added to a ethanolic solution (50 ml) of the hydrated cobalt(II) salt (0.005 mol) and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 1.5 h followed by aerobic oxidation. Upon evaporation of the resulting solution at room temperature, large dark brown crystals gradually precipitated out in each case. This was then

filtered off; washed with aqueous ethanol, and dried in air. The yield was ~70% in each case.

Syntheses of $[\text{Ni}(\text{HMPzPyr})_2]\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ and NO_3) : A hot ethanolic solution (50 ml) of the hydrated nickel(II) salt (0.005 mol) was mixed with a ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol, 2.37 g). The resulting solution was refluxed for 30 min in water bath and the clear green solution was concentrated on water bath to half of its original volume and then cooled to room temperature. The desired complex, in each case, separated out as needle shaped crystals. The compound was filtered off, washed with alcohol, and dried over fused CaCl_2 . The complexes were recrystallized from ethanol to have the analytically

pure samples. The yield was ~60% in each case.

Synthesis of $[\text{Ni}(\text{MPzPyr})_2]$: A hot methanolic solution (10 ml) of hydrated nickel(II) chloride (0.003 mol, 0.71 g) was mixed with a methanolic solution (30 ml) of the ligand (0.006 mol, 1.42 g) followed by dropwise addition of dilute ammonia to have pH around 6. A brown precipitation formed when the resulting solution was refluxed for half an hour. The product was filtered off, washed with methanol, and dried over fused calcium chloride. Yield was ~50%.

Syntheses of $[\text{Cu}(\text{MPzPyr})\text{X}]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ and NO_3) : On mixing a copper(II) salt (0.01 mol) in 50 ml of acetonitrile with the ligand (0.01 mol, 2.37 g) in the same solvent (50 ml); a bright green colored complex separated out on concentration of the resulting solution in each case. The desired complexes were washed with acetonitrile, collected, and dried over calcium chloride. The yield was ~60% in each case.

Conclusion :

On the basis of available physicochemical data on the present metal ion complexes of HMPzPyr along with reasonable discussion offered, it may be concluded that the ligand coordinates through the tertiary nitrogen atom of the pyrazole ring, the nitrogen atom of the azomethine linkage and the sulphur atom of the thiocarbonyl group in case of 1 : 1 electrolytic cobalt(III), non-electrolyte nickel(II) and copper(II) species, having the deprotonated ligand in its thiol form; while in the electrolytic bis-nickel(II) species, $[\text{Ni}(\text{HMPzPyr})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, the ligand, HMPzPyr, exhibits neutral NNS function. The reported metal complexes of cobalt(III) and nickel(II) are mostly octahedral while the copper(II) complexes are square planar.

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